

MICROBIOMES4SOY

Practice Abstracts -

batch 1

Deliverable D6.5

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Date: 14.07.2025

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Document ID

D.6.5

Due date

30 June 2025

Submission date

14 July 2025

Deliverable type

R - document, report

Dissemination level

Public

Work package

WP 6

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Project number	101083671
Duration	60 months
Start date	January 2024
End date	December 2028
Acronym	MICROBIOMES4SOY
Full name	Healthier diets and sustainable food and feed systems through employing microbes for soya production and further use
Project URL	www.microbiomes4soy.eu
EU project officer	Guido Giudetti

Table of contents

Executive Summary	5
Introduction.....	5
1.1. Objective and scope	5
2. Practice Abstracts	6
3. Conclusion	11
Contact and details	12

Executive Summary

Deliverable 6.5 "Practice abstracts - batch 1" of MICROBIOMES4SOY aims to disseminate project's results using the EIP-AGRI common format. The EIP common format consists of a set of basic elements characterising the project. The format was developed with two main objectives: (1) to enable contacting partners and incentivise efficient knowledge exchange, and (2) to disseminate the results of the project in a concise and easily understandable way to practitioners.¹

Both Horizon multi-actor projects, as MICROBIOMES4SOY, and thematic networks, along with all EIP AGRI Operational Groups, use a common format to deliver short, concise practical information (known as 'practice abstracts') to farmers, foresters, advisers, or anyone interested. The adoption of the EIP-AGRI common format enhances knowledge exchange and fosters connections between potential partners in innovation projects. This approach contributes to building a unique repository of practical knowledge across the EU through the EIP-AGRI project database, which supports the dissemination of results from all interactive innovation projects.

This comprehensive approach ensures that the valuable insights and findings from the MICROBIOMES4SOY project are accessible to a wider audience, facilitating knowledge transfer and practical application across diverse agricultural communities. The practice abstracts of the project's exploitable results realized during the first half of the project underscore our commitment to fostering innovation and collaboration within the EU food sector.

Introduction

1.1. Objective and scope

The objective of this deliverable is to provide project results in the EIP-AGRI common format. The EIP-AGRI common format enhances knowledge exchange on innovative and practice-oriented projects from their inception to completion. Additionally, this format allows farmers, advisors, researchers, and other stakeholders across the EU to easily connect. Below, the first batch of five general practice abstracts can be found.

¹ [annex to eip guidelines on eip common format - 16 march 2016 0.pdf](#)

2. Practice Abstracts

2.1 Co-developing transition pathways for sustainable Food Systems in Europe: Insights from Microbiomes4Soy

MICROBIOMES4SOY co-develops regional transition pathways with stakeholders to advance sustainable, plant-based protein diets by integrating microbiome applications into food and feed systems, aligned with EU FOOD 2030 priorities.

Hence, the project is dedicated to co-developing regional transition pathways with food system stakeholders to enable a shift toward sustainable, plant-based protein diets. The focus is on integrating microbiome applications into plant-based food and feed systems, in line with the EU's FOOD 2030 priorities. This is achieved by engaging diverse stakeholders—including farmers, advisors, industry, and policymakers—to identify leverage points for transforming food systems. This task applies a participatory, co-creation approach to identify leverage points and develop solutions with practitioners, industry, and policymakers.

Key achievements include:

- Structured workshops with stakeholders to map out transition pathways that account for impacts on education, innovation, and regulation. These sessions identify concrete actions that can lead to systemic change in food systems.
- Development of educational materials—factsheets, webinars, and tutorials—targeting stakeholders across the soya bean value chain to increase understanding of the role and benefits of microbiomes in plant protein systems.
- Identification of innovation opportunities that support sustainable plant protein production, including microbiome-based approaches in crop cultivation, feed systems, and product development. The task also explores viable business models and value chain improvements.
- Co-development of policy and regulatory recommendations to address barriers to the adoption of microbiome applications in agriculture and food production.
- A comprehensive meta-analysis of data from across the project to reveal key microbiome patterns and their potential benefits along the food and feed value chain, supporting decision-making for stakeholders.

Additional information

Transition pathways offer a powerful framework for navigating complex systemic change—particularly relevant in the context of food system transformation through microbiome applications. Unlike strategies that prescribe fixed steps, pathways map the scope, timing, and factors required to move from today’s food system toward a more sustainable future.

Transition pathways in relation to microbiomes in the food system refer to the strategic shifts needed to harness microbial communities for sustainable and resilient food production. Within the MICROBIOMES4SOY project, transition pathways are applied to foster co-developed, stakeholder-driven approaches that support the adoption of plant-based protein systems enhanced by microbiome science. These pathways consider barriers and opportunities at every stage—from agricultural practices and food processing to regulation and consumption.

These pathways involve changes in agricultural practices, food processing, and waste management to promote beneficial microbiomes that enhance soil health, plant productivity, food safety, and nutrition, aiming to reduce dependence on chemical inputs, lower environmental impact, and improve food system resilience to climate change and other disruptions. The structured approach ensures alignment among stakeholders—farmers, researchers, industry, and policy actors — by fostering a shared understanding of where change must occur, identifying leverage points for innovation, and enabling risk-aware, adaptive planning.

2.2 Fermented soya beans as a healthy alternative for animal proteins in aquaculture fish feed

Objective:

Aquaculture is one of the fastest growing food industries and offers a way forward to supply a growing population with sustainably produced animal protein. However, the required aquaculture feed currently contains fish meal as a protein source that derives from wild caught fish, leading to dangers of overfishing and overexploiting natural resources. To achieve sustainability, other alternatives for fish meal need to be found and fermented soya beans are a potential source for such a replacement. We aim to improve the fermentation process by searching for novel microorganisms and enzymes that are capable of fermenting soya beans at higher temperature to reduce the occurrence of Anti-Nutritional Factors (ANFs), compounds that reduce the availability of nutrients in the soya beans, and therefore produce a healthier fish feed.

Results:

Novel strains of bacteria have been isolated from Icelandic hot springs, capable of growing and fermenting soyabeans at higher temperatures. Together with additional bacterial strains from various other sources, more than 40 strains of bacteria are tested to find the best one's capable of fermenting soya beans and reducing ANFs. Fermentation of soya beans, using the best bacterial strains, will be optimized and upscaled for the production of protein to be included into an aquaculture fish feed formula. Fish feeding trials will be performed to observe the effect of the fermented soya bean replacement on the fish performance, health and gut microbiome and compare it to a traditional feed formula.

Practical implications/recommendations:

The novel fish feed formula based on fermented soya beans will offer the aquaculture industry a sustainable alternative to fishmeal-based feeds with tested health and performance benefits.

2.3 Investigating the gut microbiome effects of replacing dietary animal protein with plant protein

Objective: A switch from consuming animal protein to plant protein instead offers considerable benefits for sustainability, and potentially also for consumer health. Excessive animal protein consumption in red meat affects the host directly, but there also indirect effects mediated by the gut microbiome. We test the effect of a diet replacing red meat with a combination of tofu and miso instead, on the gut microbiome, using nucleic acid sequencing technologies to investigate microbiome composition and function.

Expected results:

- We will confirm the absence of toxins in soya beans grown and harvested using natural soil microbes that improve plant health and resilience.
- We will determine the effect of replacing animal protein in a typical Western diet with plant-derived protein delivered in a (soya-based) tofu, by measuring the composition, function and transcription of the microbiome. These cutting-edge omics methods will provide detailed insight into the microbiome.
- We will determine the effect of the meat-tofu swap on chemicals in human blood produced by gut microbes, and the human body response, by measuring the metabolome in serum

Practical Implications:

- Evidence basis for dietary protein replacement recommendations with special reference to long-term effects wrought by the activity of the gut microbiome
- Data on how the composition of the microbiome changes when the protein source changes can inform consumer choices
- Progress in distinguishing direct and indirect microbiome-host interaction

Main benefits:

- Direct high-quality evidence from human studies, as distinct from laboratory *in vitro* trials, on diet-microbiome interaction

2.4 The effects of agricultural management on seed agronomic and nutritional quality of soya bean and on plant-associated microbiota

Agricultural management affects plant performance, yield and also soil and plant-associated microbial communities, also termed microbiota or microbiomes. Plants host very specific microbiota, which are important for plant growth and health as they contribute to nutrient provision and plant stress resilience. It can be expected that agricultural management and plant-associated microbiota also influence plant quality traits such as agronomic seed quality or the nutritional content of plants or seeds specifically.

In MICROBIOMES4SOY we assess if and how agricultural management including the application of newly developed microbial inoculants affect plant performance and seed quality. Greenhouse, lysimeter and field experiments are performed to provide information on:

- which agronomic practises favour soya bean yields and influence agronomic quality and nutritional content of soya bean seeds
- whether microbial inoculation practises, either by applying individual microbial strains or a combination of selected strains, can improve stress (e.g., drought) resilience of soya bean plants
- whether microbial inoculation practises, either by applying individual microbial strains or a

combination of selected strains, can improve seed quality aiming to achieve “microbiome-improved seeds”. Apart from agronomic traits, we will specifically address nutritional quality of seeds targeting e.g., protein content or contents of antinutritional factors.

2.5 Healthy soil, strong soybeans: Using natural microbes to boost soybean yields in Europe

Objective: European soya bean farmers face challenges with crop performance due to soil health, climate conditions, and high chemical costs. This project aims to boost soyabean yields using natural soil microbes that improve plant health and resilience.

Expected results:

- We will identify beneficial soil microbes from 100 European soyabean fields, which potentially help soya bean plants absorb nutrients, grow stronger, and resist diseases.
- We will develop AI-based models to match the right consortia of microbes with specific field conditions, ensuring effective use.
- We will test these beneficial microbes in both lab and field conditions, to identify consortia of microbes that can provide significant improvements in soya bean growth and resilience.

Practical implications:

- **Yield improvement:** Farmers can achieve better harvests using recommended beneficial microbes, while reducing input of agrochemicals.
- **Healthier crops:** With the help of the helper microbes, soya beans may become more resilient to environmental stresses with less use of agrochemicals.
- **Reduced costs:** Less need for chemical inputs means lower expenses.
- **Easy adoption:** Farmers will receive guides and online resources for learning more about how beneficial microbes can help in their crop system.

Main benefits:

- Healthier crops and reduced chemical use lead to better profits and more sustainable farming.

This project is a collaboration between European universities, research institutes, and agricultural companies to help farmers grow better soya beans using nature's own solutions.

3. Conclusion

This document presents the first batch of MICROBIOMES4SOY practice abstracts, covering a general description and some project results up to month 18. The first five practice abstracts were already uploaded on the [EU CAP Network](#) (the former EIP AGRI portal) by month 18. Using the EIP-AGRI common format facilitates the dissemination of the project's results to researchers, entrepreneurs, citizens, and other EU-funded projects. Until the end of the project in M60, we will continue to collect practice abstracts and submit the second batch as the actions of the MICROBIOMES4SOY project become increasingly concrete.

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